

Kinetic Study of the Oxidation of Ethyl Glycollate by Chromic Acid

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The kinetics of the initial stages of the oxidation of the ethyl ester of glycollic acid have been studied. The rate is proportional to the concentration of HCrO_4^- . The rate is also proportional to the concentration of ester and of hydrogen ions. The energy of activation, PZ factor and the entropy of activation have the values $14.0 \text{ Kcal mole}^{-1}$, $1.54 \times 10^8 \text{ litre}^2 \text{ mole}^{-2} \text{ sec}^{-1}$ and -23.7 e.u. respectively. From the consideration of the entropy of activation it is concluded that the rate determining step involves the rupture of C-H bond.

Sundaram and Venkatasubramanian¹ have recently studied the chromic acid oxidation of the esters of mandelic acid. Jha and Bakore² have also studied the chromic acid oxidation of the ethyl ester of mandelic acid and indicated support to the mechanism of oxidation of the mandelic acid as suggested by Bakore and Narain³, which involves rupture of C-H bond in the rate determining step. The work of the said authors suggest that the information regarding the mechanism of the oxidation of the esters of hydroxy acids is not sufficient. The present investigation was therefore undertaken. The results of the chromic acid oxidation of ethyl glycollate are reported here.

EXPERIMENTAL

Material: Chromic acid solution was prepared from "AnalaR" potassium dichromate. Glacial acetic acid was distilled over CrO_3 to remove any oxidising impurity present. Ethyl glycollate was prepared by Fischer's method⁴ and purified by redistillation. Purity was tested by b.p. determination. MnSO_4 and other reagents used were chemically pure.

Kinetic measurements: The experiments were carried out at a constant temperature ($\pm 0.02^\circ$). The solvent used was 50% glacial acetic acid. The reactants were brought to the thermostat temperature and then rapidly mixed in a bottle. The dichromate solution was last to be added. Zero time was taken as that when half of the dichromate solution was in the flask. Aliquot parts were withdrawn at known interval of time and the gross concentration of chromium was estimated by iodometric method, precaution being taken to minimise oxidation by air⁵.

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RESULTS

Rate Laws : When concentration of ester and hydrogen ions were high it was found that the rate at which chromium (VI) disappeared follows first order law.

Although the rate at which chromium (VI) disappears follows first order law, the value is not independent of the initial concentration of the chromium (VI). An increase in the concentration of the chromium (VI) decreases the value of first order rate constant. This result suggests that HCrO_4^- is the active oxidising species⁵ (cf. Table 1).

TABLE 1

Variation of Rate with Concentration of Chromium (VI)
 (Ester) : $1.54 \times 10^{-2} M$
 (H^+) : $1.60 M$ Temperature : 35°

$\text{Cr(VI)} \times 10^3$ moles litre ⁻¹	$(\text{HCrO}_4^-) \times 10^3$ moles litre ⁻¹	$k_1 \times 10^2$ min ⁻¹	$10^2 k_1$ (CrVI) (HCrO_4^-)
2.00	1.68	2.64	3.15
4.00	2.92	2.52	3.44
6.00	4.00	2.32	3.48
8.00	4.88	2.02	3.30
10.00	5.80	1.98	3.41

The rate is proportional to the first power of the concentration of the ester (cf. Table 2).

TABLE 2

Variation of Rate with Concentration of Ester
 Cr(VI) : $4.00 \times 10^{-3} M$
 (H^+) : $1.60 M$ Temperature : 35°

(Ester) $\times 10^2$ moles litre ⁻¹	$k_1 \times 10^2$ min ⁻¹	$k_1/(\text{Ester})$ moles ⁻¹ litre min ⁻¹
0.769	1.00	1.30
1.54	2.50	1.62
2.31	3.40	1.47
3.08	4.62	1.50
3.85	5.78	1.47

The rate is proportional to the first power of the concentration of hydrogen ions (cf. Table 3).

TABLE 3

Variation of Rate with Concentration of Hydrogen Ions

(Ester) : $1.54 \times 10^{-2} M$		
[Cr(VI)] : $4.00 \times 10^{-3} M$ Temperature : 35°		
(H) ⁺ moles litre ⁻¹	$k_1 \times 10^2$ min ⁻¹	$10^2 k_1 / (H^+)$ moles ⁻¹ litre min ⁻¹
0.320	0.500	1.56
0.640	1.00	1.56
0.800	1.20	1.50
1.60	2.51	1.58
4.00	6.10	1.53

Effect of solvent composition : Increase in the proportion of acetic acid in the solvent mixture increased the rate of oxidation (cf. Table 4).

TABLE 4

Effect of Solvent Composition on Rate

(Ester) : $1.54 \times 10^{-2} M$	
[Cr(VI)] : $4.00 \times 10^{-3} M$	
(H ⁺) : $1.60 M$	
Temperature : 35°	
% Glacial acetic acid (v/v)	$k_1 \times 10^2$ min ⁻¹
20	1.050
30	1.70
40	2.01
50	2.50
80	3.84

In the presence of acetic acid the rate is affected by one or more of the following reasons :

(i) Increase in acetic acid decreases dielectric constant⁶ of the solvent and consequently increases the protonation of $HCrO_4^-$, which leads to increased rate of oxidation.

(ii) The possibility of the formation of acetyl chromic acid $CH_3.CO.CrO_2OH$ or its conjugated acid $CH_3.CO.CrO_2OH_2^+$, in acetic acid medium. These are strong acids and more powerful oxidising agents as compared to chromic acid H_2CrO_4 ^{7,8}.

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It is however difficult to precisely state the contribution of each factor with increase in the proportion of acetic acid in the solvent mixture.

Effect of Manganous Ions on Rate : Addition of manganous ions decreases the rate of oxidation. The rate of oxidation reaches a limiting value, when the concentration of manganous ions, $\leq 2.00 \times 10^{-3} M$ and under these conditions the rate of oxidation in presence of manganous ions is about one third the rate in absence of manganous ions. (cf. Table 5). This suggests that probably chromic acid is involved as an intermediate.²

TABLE 5

Effect of Manganous Ions on Rate

(Ester) : $1.54 \times 10^{-2} M$ (H⁺) : $1.60 M$
 [Cr(VI)] : $4.00 \times 10^{-3} M$ Temperature : 35°

[Mn(II)] $\times 10^3$ moles litre ⁻¹	$k_1 \times 10^2$ min ⁻¹
—	2.51
2.00	1.43
6.00	1.39
10.00	1.16
20.00	0.930

Effect of temperature : The reaction was studied at temperatures 25, 29, 35 and 40°. The rate constants at these temperatures are summarised in Table 6. The specific rates were obtained from the observed first order rate constant from the relation :

$$k = k_1 / (\text{Ester})(\text{H}^+)$$

These are given in Table 6, column 3. The heat of activation, PZ factor and entropy of activation calculated from data in Table 6, have the values 14.0 Kcal moles⁻¹, 1.54×10^8 litre² mole⁻¹ sec⁻¹ and -23.7 e.u. respectively.

TABLE 6

Effect of Temperature on Rate

(Ester) : $1.54 \times 10^{-2} M$ (H⁺) : $1.60 M$
 [Cr(VI)] : $4.00 \times 10^{-3} M$

Temperature °K	$k_1 \times 10^2$ min ⁻¹	$k \times 10^2$ mole ⁻² litre ² sec ⁻¹
298	1.17	0.798
302	1.61	1.09
308	2.52	1.71
313	3.55	2.40

DISCUSSION

Sundaram and Venkatasubramanian¹ have recently studied the chromic acid oxidation of the esters of mandelic acid and have suggested cyclic hydride-ion transfer mechanism. Our results can, however, be explained by an ester mechanism involving a proton loss^{9,10,11}.

Thus, the mechanism of the oxidation of ethyl glycollate involves rapid and reversible formation of the chromate ester, which then decomposes by a cyclic mechanism, that the decomposition of the chromate ester is the rate determining step in which C-H bond is ruptured with the loss of hydrogen proton.

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